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**PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES IN HR: COMPARATIVE
ANALYSIS AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION**

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Abstract. *Modern human resource management practices in the context of digital transformation demonstrate a shift in emphasis from routine administrative functions to strategic change management and the initiation of complex projects. HR departments are increasingly becoming key participants in organizational development programs, including the implementation of HR information systems, digitalization of personnel document flow, optimization of employee selection and adaptation processes, formation of corporate culture and development of remuneration systems. The increasing complexity and interdisciplinary nature of such initiatives require the use of modern project management methodologies that can ensure a balance of flexibility, structure and controllability.*

The article presents a comparative analysis of five methodological approaches — Agile, Scrum, Kanban, Waterfall, and Hybrid — from the standpoint of their adaptability to the HR context. The mechanisms by which flexible methodologies help minimize response time to changing conditions, enhance feedback with internal clients, and increase team engagement are analyzed. The advantages of structured approaches that provide a high degree of predictability and control over project parameters in the context of stable requirements are studied. The specifics of hybrid models that integrate elements of various methodologies to achieve an optimal balance between implementation speed, result quality, and resource efficiency are highlighted.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in substantiating the need for methodological adaptation of project management to the specifics of HR activities and in forming a systematized algorithm for selecting an approach taking into account the nature of tasks, the level of uncertainty, the maturity of the project culture and the specifics of the corporate environment. The practical significance of the study is expressed in the possibility of applying its results to develop strategies and regulations for the implementation of project methodologies in HR departments, which allows for increased manageability of changes, accelerated implementation of innovations and the formation of a sustainable project culture within the organization.

Keywords: *project management, HR, Agile, Scrum, Kanban, Waterfall, Hybrid, digital transformation, project culture, organizational change.*

The transformation of modern business, caused by the acceleration of technological progress, globalization of markets and digitalization of key processes, has a direct impact on the strategic role of HR services in organizations. The classical model of their functioning, focused primarily on

personnel administration, is increasingly giving way to a model of strategic partnership, where HR becomes not only a conductor of organizational policy, but also an active initiator of change [1].

The implementation of modern HR information systems, automation of document flow, development of training and adaptation programs, formation of corporate culture and motivation system - all this requires a comprehensive approach to planning, implementation and control of initiatives. The growing complexity of HR projects is associated with many factors: the interdisciplinary nature of tasks, the high dynamics of the external environment, the need to involve various categories of internal stakeholders, as well as limited resources and deadlines.

In the face of such challenges, traditional linear approaches to work organization become insufficient. The lack of flexibility and adaptation tools slows down the implementation of changes, increases the risk of missed deadlines, and worsens the quality of the final result. That is why project management methodologies, widely used in IT, engineering, and marketing, are beginning to actively penetrate the HR environment. At the same time, their application requires not direct copying, but adaptation taking into account the specifics of HR processes and corporate culture [2].

In recent years, five methodological approaches have become the most widespread: Agile, Scrum, Kanban, Waterfall and Hybrid. Each of them has its own set of advantages and limitations that determine the appropriateness of use in a particular type of HR projects. Flexible methodologies allow you to quickly respond to changing requirements and ensure transparency of interaction with internal clients. Classic cascade approaches ensure predictability, clear planning and control, which is especially important in projects with fixed requirements. Hybrid models combine the strengths of different approaches and allow you to take into account the individual characteristics of the organization.

Despite the obvious potential for using these methodologies in HR, the issue of choosing the optimal model remains debatable. This is due to the fact that HR projects vary significantly in terms of uncertainty, duration, complexity, and the degree of impact on the organization as a whole. Therefore, a systematic approach is needed to compare the characteristics of the project with the parameters of the methodology and determine the best match.

The purpose of the article is a comparative analysis of five key project management methodologies in order to identify their applicability in the HR context. The paper examines the principles of adapting methodologies to the specifics of HR processes, develops recommendations for their selection and implementation, and forms a methodological basis for developing a project culture in HR departments.

Historically, HR functions were focused on operational and administrative activities: personnel records management, timekeeping, payroll, and compliance with labor laws. This format of work corresponded to the industrial economy, where personnel policy was stable and changes occurred relatively slowly.

The transition to a knowledge economy, increased competition for talent, and the growing importance of human capital in creating added value have changed the role of HR in an organization. Today, the HR function covers a wide range of strategic tasks: forming a corporate culture, developing leadership, managing changes, implementing digital technologies, and building adaptive employment models [3-5]. These tasks are essentially project-based — they have clearly defined goals, limited timeframes, resource frameworks, and success criteria.

That is why, in the last two decades, HR departments have begun to master the project approach, borrowing and adapting methodologies originally developed for IT, engineering and manufacturing. Project management in HR allows you to systematize activities, improve the manageability of initiatives, ensure transparency of interaction with stakeholders and minimize the risks of missed deadlines and budget overruns.

Unlike technical or production projects, HR projects have a pronounced social and organizational nature. Their results are directly related to the behavior, motivation and involvement of people, and the effect of the implemented solutions is often delayed. Key features of HR projects: human-centricity — the final “product” of the project is changes in the competencies, behavior, or

satisfaction of employees ; multi-level impact — the project affects both the individual and team, organizational levels; uncertainty of initial conditions — the requirements and expectations of stakeholders may change during the implementation process; the need for communication support — the success of the project largely depends on the quality of information support and the readiness of employees to change; integration with corporate culture — incompatibility of the methodology with the values and norms of the company can lead to resistance to change. These features determine the need for flexible, adaptive, but at the same time manageable implementation methods.

Among modern approaches to project management, several can be identified that are most applicable to HR [6-13]: Agile is a flexible development philosophy focused on adapting to changes and constant interaction with the customer. In HR, this approach is used for rapid testing of initiatives, iterative improvement of employee training and adaptation programs, as well as in cultural transformation projects ; Scrum is a structured framework within Agile, providing for work in short cycles (sprints), with a clear distribution of roles and regular team meetings. Suitable for HR projects where intermediate results and high intensity of interaction are important; Kanban is a method for visualizing the flow of tasks and managing the team's workload. In HR, it is used to optimize work with recruitment applications, training requests, and employee inquiries; Waterfall is a cascade model that involves sequential completion of project stages. It is effective in HR projects with fixed requirements, such as implementing payroll or electronic document management systems; Hybrid is a combined approach that combines elements of various methodologies. In HR, it is appropriate for large-scale transformation initiatives when strategic planning requires structure, and operational tasks require flexibility.

One of the key factors for the successful application of methodologies is the level of development of the project culture in the HR department [14-16]. The project culture includes the awareness of the value of the project approach by all participants; proficiency in planning, monitoring and analysis tools; ability to work in cross-functional teams; readiness to manage change and risks; the existence of a mechanism for exchanging knowledge and best practices. A developed project culture allows HR departments not only to apply the chosen methodology, but also to adapt it to their own tasks, achieving a higher level of efficiency and sustainability of results.

Theoretical analysis shows that the implementation of project methodologies in HR is not a simple transfer of tools from other areas, but a process of adaptation taking into account the specifics of HR processes, the human factor and the organizational environment. The choice of approach should take into account the nature of the project, the degree of uncertainty, resource constraints and the team's readiness for self-organization. It is the combination of the methodological base and project culture that determines the ability of the HR service to become a driver of change in the organization.

The use of project methodologies in the HR environment requires consideration of a number of factors that are not always critical in technical or production projects [17-20]. Firstly, HR projects directly affect the interests of a wide range of internal stakeholders – from line employees to top management, which determines the high importance of communication strategy and change management. Secondly, a significant part of the results of HR projects is intangible, which complicates the measurement of efficiency and requires the use of complex KPIs, including both quantitative and qualitative indicators.

The methodology should be adapted to the maturity level of the HR team, corporate culture and scale of the initiative. Thus, flexible approaches are effective when there is a need for rapid testing and refinement of solutions, while cascade models are appropriate in stable, strictly regulated processes.

Agile is not a specific methodology, but a holistic project management philosophy, enshrined in *the Agile Manifesto*, which emphasizes the values of flexibility, collaboration, and focus on results [7]. The key idea of Agile is the readiness to constantly adapt solutions in response to changing conditions and customer needs. In the HR context, the customer is not only top management, but also internal clients - department heads, line managers, employees involved in the process.

Unlike traditional models, where a project is planned in full and implemented strictly in stages, Agile assumes an iterative approach: a product or service is created and improved in small portions, and each iteration ends with the receipt of a working result available for testing and evaluation.

Agile is especially effective in situations where the initial requirements for a project are partially uncertain or may change as the work progresses; it is important to quickly test hypotheses and make prompt adjustments; The project has a strong human and cultural component that requires the involvement of participants. Typical HR projects where Agile demonstrates high efficiency include the development and implementation of employee onboarding programs, where the first modules can be launched even before the completion of the entire program; creation of corporate training platforms and courses, allowing the release of individual courses as they become ready; projects to develop corporate culture, where it is important to test initiatives on individual groups and scale up successful solutions; pilot HR innovations, such as the introduction of chatbots for communication with employees or gamification systems for motivation.

Key Agile mechanisms adapted to the HR environment include [7] iterative development of solutions - regular short work cycles with mandatory analysis of results; continuous feedback from internal clients to promptly identify and resolve any non-conformities; prioritizing tasks based on business value and employee needs; self-organization of the team and distributed responsibility.

An important tool in Agile for HR is short meetings, which allow the team to synchronize actions, identify obstacles and make decisions quickly.

Advantages of Agile for HR: the ability to adjust the project at any stage without significant loss of time and resources; the first results appear within a few weeks after the start; regular participation of managers and employees in the formation of requirements and evaluation of results; identification and elimination of problems at early stages.

Limitations and risks of using Agile in HR: the need for a mature team; difficulties in budgeting; incompatibility with rigid hierarchical structures; risk of “blurring” of goals [7].

Conditions for successful implementation of Agile in HR : support from management and willingness to delegate authority to teams; training HR staff in Agile principles and tools; availability of infrastructure (task management systems, communication channels, analytical tools); clear definition of areas of responsibility and performance indicators at each stage. Thus, Agile in HR practice is a powerful tool for accelerated implementation of initiatives in conditions of high uncertainty and the need for flexibility. It allows HR departments not only to respond faster to business demands, but also to form a culture of continuous improvement, involving employees in the change process. However, to achieve a sustainable effect, organizational readiness, a mature project culture and the ability to balance between operational adaptation and strategic goals are required.

Scrum is a structured framework within the Agile philosophy, designed to manage projects in conditions of high dynamics and the need to regularly obtain tangible results. Unlike the general Agile approach, Scrum clearly regulates roles, artifacts and events, which allows you to maintain process control while maintaining flexibility [8].

In the HR context, Scrum is especially in demand in projects that require serial implementation of similar tasks, high intensity of team interaction and constant verification of intermediate results.

Scrum has proven itself in the following scenarios: mass recruiting, where each sprint can be dedicated to recruiting candidates for a specific department or region; assessment centers and assessment activities carried out in batches by groups of employees; launching corporate educational programs, when individual modules are designed, tested and implemented in stages; implementation of HR technologies, such as onboarding systems or digital engagement tools, where a fast “development-test-adjustment” cycle is important.

Roles in Scrum and their adaptation to HR. Product Owner (product owner) - in HR, this role is often performed by the HR director or project manager, who defines the goals, priorities and expected results. Scrum Master — a coordinator who ensures compliance with Scrum principles, removal of organizational barriers and effective team communication. This role can be performed by an HR project manager. Development (implementation) team - in HR, this is a cross-functional group

of specialists (recruiters, HR analysts, business partners, trainers) who directly carry out the sprint tasks.

Scrum Artifacts in HR . Product Backlog - a complete list of all required project tasks (e.g. vacancies to close, training modules, communication activities). Sprint Backlog is a set of tasks selected for completion within a specific sprint. An increment is a finished result of a sprint that can be demonstrated to the customer: a fully staffed team, a finished course module, and a completed assessment.

Scrum Events in HR . Sprint Planning — defining sprint goals and scope of work. Daily Stand-Ups - Short synchronization meetings to monitor progress. Sprint review - presenting the results to internal clients and collecting feedback. Retrospective is a discussion of what can be improved in the next cycle.

Advantages of Scrum for HR. Transparency of processes - all participants and customers see at what stage the project is. Regular feedback - the customer receives the result in stages and can promptly adjust the requirements. Flexibility within the structure - the ability to make changes between sprints without losing control. Increased team engagement - all team members are actively involved in planning and reviewing work .

Limitations and risks of Scrum in HR. Risk of overload - if the tasks are assessed incorrectly, the team may face excessive workload. High demands on discipline - it is necessary to strictly adhere to the rhythm of sprints and accepted procedures. The Need for Experienced Scrum Master - the lack of a qualified coordinator reduces efficiency. Cultural barriers - in organizations with a rigid hierarchy, the principles of self-organization may encounter resistance.

Conditions for successful implementation of Scrum in HR. Training the team in Scrum principles and their adaptation to HR processes; management support that allows the team to work autonomously within sprints; realistic sprint planning taking into account the actual workload of employees; using digital tools (Trello, Jira, MS Planner) to manage backlog and tasks. Thus, Scrum in HR combines flexibility with high structure, which makes it especially valuable in projects with limited deadlines and the need to quickly deliver intermediate results. However, its successful application requires a prepared team, support at the management level, and the organization's commitment to a culture of transparency and continuous improvement.

Kanban is a visual task management method that originated from the Toyota Production System and has become widely used in project management due to its simplicity, clarity, and ability to effectively allocate resources. Unlike Scrum and other flexible frameworks, Kanban does not require radical restructuring of processes or strictly regulated cycles [9]. It allows for gradual implementation of improvements without interrupting current activities, which makes it especially popular in HR departments with high operational loads.

Kanban method is especially effective where the HR service works with a constant flow of similar requests and tasks that require control at all stages of execution. Such processes include tracking the status of each vacancy from the moment the application is received until the employee starts work; recording incoming applications, coordinating, organizing training and summing up the results; processing requests on issues of personnel administration, benefits, compensation; implementation and support of HR tools - for example, automation of vacation calculations, collection and processing of feedback on HR services.

Kanban principles in the HR context. Visualization of the workflow - all tasks are reflected on the Kanban board (physical or digital), divided into stages ("Incoming", "In progress", "Under approval", "Completed"). WIP limitation - limiting the number of tasks in progress at the same time to avoid overloading the team and ensure a stable flow of execution. Incremental improvements - changes to the process are made evolutionarily, based on an analysis of the current workload and bottlenecks. Transparency and shared responsibility - all team members have access to task status information, increasing engagement and reducing the risk of delays.

Benefits of using Kanban in HR. Allows you to instantly assess the workload and progress of the work. Does not require global reorganization of processes. Limiting WIP helps to distribute work evenly among employees. Analysis of "bottlenecks" leads to increased efficiency of processes.

Limitations and risks of using Kanban in HR. No strict deadlines; risk of incoming flow overload; dependence on team discipline; efficiency Kanban declines if members do not update task statuses.

Practical implementation of Kanban in HR in modern HR services, Kanban is most often implemented using digital tools: Trello, Jira, Asana, Microsoft Planner. This allows boards to be integrated with corporate HRIS systems; set up automatic notifications about a task moving to the next stage; conduct analytics on execution time, bottlenecks and employee workload.

Conditions for successful application of Kanban in HR: regular updating of task statuses on the board; defining WIP limits to prevent overload; implementation of task prioritization based on criteria of urgency and importance; training employees in the principles of visual management and self-organization. Thus, Kanban is an optimal tool for managing constant task flows in HR, providing transparency, load balancing and the ability to smoothly increase efficiency without abrupt organizational changes. However, for maximum effect, it must be supplemented with prioritization and deadline control mechanisms, which will avoid delays in tasks and maintain a stable work rhythm.

The Waterfall model is one of the earliest and most formalized approaches to project management, in which the entire project is divided into clear sequential stages, and the transition to the next is possible only after the previous one has been fully completed. The concept has become widespread in engineering and IT projects, but it continues to be used in the HR sphere where tasks require strict regulation and minimal variability.

Unlike agile methodologies, Waterfall assumes that all project requirements can be defined in advance, and changes at later stages are highly undesirable. For HR, this can be useful in situations where legislation, regulations, or corporate standards do not allow flexible interpretation of processes.

Using Waterfall in HR. Waterfall is well suited for projects of development and implementation of HR policies and regulations, where multi-stage approval is required; large-scale certification and assessment of personnel, carried out according to a single approved plan; implementation of HRIS systems, when integration affects key databases and must proceed strictly according to the project plan; conducting mandatory training programs (for example, on labor protection or compliance), which cannot be changed during the implementation process.

Waterfall stages in an HR project. Initiation and requirements analysis – formulation of goals, objectives and expected results; in HR this may include analysis of current processes, regulatory requirements, resource constraints. Design is the detailed development of the plan, project structure, schedule and responsible persons. Implementation is the execution of planned activities in strict accordance with the approved plan. Testing and verification is the quality control of project execution; in HR, it is the verification of the correctness of the implemented procedures and systems. Implementation and handover into operation – final implementation of the solution and its handover into operation. Maintenance – support and adjustment within the framework of regulatory restrictions.

Advantages of Waterfall in HR: full project specification at the start; each stage has a completed result, which simplifies execution control; convenient when working with mandatory regulations; suitable for large and distributed teams where strict management is required.

Limitations and risks of Waterfall in HR: making changes at late stages requires significant resources; risk of the end result not meeting current needs during long-term implementation; lack of intermediate results for evaluation and course correction; long implementation cycles, which can reduce the involvement of participants.

Conditions for successful application of Waterfall in HR : absence of expected significant changes in the project process; defining a mandatory order of actions; team readiness to strictly adhere to schedules and procedures; use of control tools (Gantt charts, corporate PM systems).

Thus, Waterfall remains relevant for HR projects that require a high degree of formalization and stability, especially in the context of strict regulatory restrictions. However, when implemented

in a dynamic business environment, one should take into account its lack of flexibility and the possibility of lagging behind the rapidly changing needs of the organization.

Hybrid models are a combination of elements of traditional (Waterfall) and flexible (Agile, Scrum, Kanban) approaches, adapted to specific project conditions. Their key feature is the ability to simultaneously maintain the structure and control inherent in cascade models and provide the flexibility and adaptability inherent in Agile methodologies.

In the HR environment, hybrid approaches are especially in demand in projects that simultaneously include strictly regulated blocks (for example, compliance with legal requirements, HR administration) and dynamic, creative tasks (for example, development of corporate training programs or engagement events).

Examples of successful application of hybrid models: implementation of HRIS or ERP systems, where technical integration requires a cascade structure, and user interface development and testing can be carried out using Agile; creation of corporate training programs, where mandatory modules are developed using Waterfall, and additional ones are developed using Scrum for quick adaptation to requests; corporate culture transformation projects, where the strategic framework is set by a traditional model, and individual initiatives are tested in pilots using agile methodologies; large-scale onboarding and recruiting programs where the basic procedures are fixed, but the communication and interaction mechanisms can be improved iteratively.

Principles of hybrid management in HR. Dividing the project into stability zones and flexibility zones; integration of tools; control of different rhythms; the role of the HR project office.

Benefits of Hybrid in HR. Ability to meet requirements and simultaneously respond to changes; formalization of costly and critical stages, acceleration of creative and experimental ones; adjustments can be made to parts of the project without disrupting the overall plan; a combination of tools allows minimizing the likelihood of missed deadlines or inconsistency of the result.

Limitations and risks of Hybrid in HR: Complexity of coordination; risk of “blurring” of methodology; increased communication requirements; dependence on the competence of the project manager.

Conditions for successful implementation of Hybrid in HR: Clear decomposition of the project into fixed and flexible parts; defining a single point of control (project manager or project office) to ensure consistency of processes; training participants in both traditional and flexible working methods; use of digital integration tools (e.g. MS Project + Jira, Trello + corporate ERP). Thus, hybrid management models allow HR departments to build projects taking into account both the need for strict compliance with regulations and the need for rapid adaptation of solutions. This makes them especially valuable in the context of digital transformation, when HR simultaneously solves the problems of technological integration and increasing employee engagement. However, the successful use of Hybrid requires a highly mature project culture, a clear communication structure, and experience in managing mixed teams.

The decision to use a particular methodology should be based on an analysis of: the nature of the project (innovative, operational, infrastructural); level of uncertainty (stable requirements or changing conditions); implementation deadlines (short-term initiatives or long-term programs); team maturity (experience working with flexible or structured models); corporate culture (openness to experimentation or focus on regulations).

The analysis showed that there is no universal methodology for all HR projects. Efficiency depends on the context, goals, and the team’s readiness for change. Flexible approaches ensure speed and adaptability, but require high levels of self-organization. Cascade models guarantee stability and control, but are less suited to rapidly changing conditions. Hybrid solutions help find a balance, but their implementation requires experience and a developed project culture (table 1).

Table 1 — Comparative methodology of application in HR

Methodology	Typical HR projects	Key Benefits	Main limitations
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Agile	Adaptation programs, cultural development projects, pilot initiatives	High flexibility, fast response to feedback	It is difficult to predict the timing and budget
Scrum	Assessment centers, corporate training launch, mass recruitment campaigns	Clear structure, high speed sprints	Risk of team overload
Kanban	Recruitment, processing of training applications, support of internal services	Visibility, load balance	There are no strict deadlines
Waterfall	Implementation of HRIS, electronic document management, development of job descriptions	Predictability, control	Low flexibility, risk of delays in changes
Hybrid	Reform of the remuneration system, implementation of HR policies	Balancing control and adaptability	Difficulty of management and coordination

Analysis of the collected data showed that the choice of project management methodology in HR is largely determined by the level of uncertainty of the initial conditions, the scale of the initiative and the team's readiness for self-organization. At the same time, there is no universal approach that is equally effective for all categories of projects: a methodology that demonstrates high results in one context may be of little use in another.

It has been found that flexible methodologies (Agile, Scrum) have an advantage in projects where the key success factor is the ability to quickly adapt to changes and promptly provide interim results. In turn, structured approaches (Waterfall) remain relevant in long-term initiatives with fixed requirements, and Kanban is widely used in supporting and operational processes. Hybrid models demonstrate sustainable results in complex transformation programs where it is necessary to combine strategic planning and operational adaptation.

Based on the analysis conducted, a number of principles can be identified that allow HR departments to make an informed choice of approach to project management: The methodology should reflect the nature of the task: flexible approaches for initiatives with high uncertainty, structured approaches for projects with fixed parameters, hybrid approaches for complex transformations; with low readiness for self-organization, a methodology with a clear structure and fixed roles is preferable; with high readiness, flexible and adaptive models can be used; The methodology should fit organically into the value system and accepted management practices of the company; The choice of approach should take into account the availability of human, time and financial resources; The methodology should provide mechanisms for communication and stakeholder involvement, especially in projects with a strong cultural and organizational impact.

In order to simplify the process of selecting a methodology, it is advisable to use a matrix in which the type of project is compared with priorities and the level of uncertainty (table 2):

Table 2 — Type of HR project

Type of HR project	Level of uncertainty	Priority goals	Recommended methodology
Mass recruitment in a short time frame	Average	Speed, quality control	Scrum
Launch of a corporate training program	High	Flexibility, adaptation	Agile

Support for incoming HR requests	Short	Transparency, load optimization	Kanban
Implementation of HRIS or ERP module	Short	Predictability, control	Waterfall
Reform of the remuneration system	Medium / High	Balance between flexibility & structure	Hybrid

For the successful implementation of project methodologies in HR practice, the following algorithm is recommended: process diagnostics; **selection** of a pilot project; team training; piloting; analysis of results; scaling; continuous improvement. In the process of integrating project methodologies into HR work, risks are possible that require advance management: staff resistance; lack of competence; team overload; mismatch with corporate culture.

Strategic recommendations: Create internal centers of excellence, exchange of experience and best practices. Train HR teams in multiple approaches and build the ability to combine them. Assess not only operational performance, but also the strategic impact of the project on the organization. The conducted research confirmed that the application of project management methodologies in HR practice is not simply borrowing tools from related areas, but requires their targeted adaptation to the specifics of HR processes, the human factor and organizational culture. The choice of approach directly depends on the type of project, the degree of uncertainty, the maturity of the team and the strategic priorities of the organization.

Flexible methodologies such as Agile and Scrum demonstrate high efficiency in dynamic projects with changing requirements, allowing for quick response to feedback and continuous interaction with internal customers. Kanban has proven itself as an effective tool for managing a constant flow of tasks and optimizing team workload. Waterfall remains relevant in long-term infrastructure projects with fixed parameters, providing stability and control. Hybrid approaches allow combining the advantages of different models, which is especially valuable when implementing complex transformations.

Prospects for further research are seen in an in-depth study of the influence of corporate culture on the success of implementing various methodologies, the development of integration models that allow combining elements of several approaches within one project, as well as in the analysis of the influence of digital tools on the development of project culture in HR.

Thus, in the context of digital transformation and growing competition for human capital, mastery of project methodologies is becoming for HR not an additional skill, but a key competence that determines the ability of the HR service to be a strategic partner of the business and a driver of organizational change.

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